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AIRE is expressed in lymph node metastases.

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Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer (1); metastasis to the lymph nodes in breast cancer is dangerous, relatively common, and in one study ranged from 10-60% based on molecular subtype (2-4). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data (5). We pioneered understanding of metastasis to the lymph nodes as an intermediate biological and anatomical counterpart to the CNS metastasis in humans (6-12). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (13, 14) for discovery and insight into clonal evolution through disease progression. We describe activation of the autoimmune regulator, AIRE, in metastasis to the lymph nodes in human breast cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes to describe the lymph node metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer.

Results

Figure 1: AIRE is differentially expressed in lymph node metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=18 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=16 lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
208090_s_at	1.92E-01	-1.3315171	-5.28341	-0.1309635	AIRE	4109/22277	81.6

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer (13), we discovered differential expression of autoimmune regulator, encoded by *AIRE* in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *AIRE* changed more than 80% of the human lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *AIRE* messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of *AIRE* during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

II. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=36 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=36 lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
208090_s_at	1.09E-01	-1.621071	-4.77586	-0.1031517	AIRE	3734/22277	83.2

Through measurement of total transcription in the lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer as compared to primary tumors of the breast, we validated differential expression of *AIRE* in metastasis to the lymph node in breast cancer (**Chart 2**) (14). The expression of *AIRE* here changed more than 80% of the lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *AIRE* messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of *AIRE* during disease progression and dissemination in humans with breast cancer.

Thus, differential and increased expression of *AIRE* defines the lymph node metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

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Discussion

We described here activation of the autoimmune regulator, AIRE, in metastasis to the lymph nodes in human breast cancer. Immune-restricted expression changes in metastasis are generally stratified as changes in gene expression resulting from or attributed to a host defense strategy, or tumor-based changes in gene expression to evade tumor surveillance or restriction of cell cycling. It is not yet understood what purpose or intent changes in AIRE during metastasis in the periphery serve.

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Methods

We utilized GSE44408 (13) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE57968 [14] for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.